

Firm growth, Size, dividend Policy and Financing Choices of Nigerian Non-Financial Firms

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Abstract

Firms financing choices has remained perpetually an object of debate in both corporate and academic discussions. This study examines the how firm growth, size and dividend policy which are rarely jointly investigated in empirical analysis of financing choices of Nigerian firms. This study also argues that firm leverage should emphasize capitalization rather than short term financing and thus measured leverage as long term debt to equity ratio. The study employed panel data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of a sample of 20 nonfinancial firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange from 2016 to 2021. The results revealed that the average debt-equity ratio of the firms was 51:49 with a coefficient of variation of 0.3647 suggesting minimal dispersion among the firms' debt ratios. The random effect regression model adopted for the study showed that firm size, growth, asset tangibility, firm age and return on assets are positively related to debt-equity ratio. Conversely, dividend policy and return on equity are negatively related to debt-ratio. However, only return on assets and return on equity are significantly related to the firms'

financing choices. The study concluded that firm size, growth, dividend policy are not the key drivers of financing choices of Nigerian non-financial firms but their level of profitability.

Keywords: Capital structure, Corporate finance, Dividend policy, Firm size, Firm growth.

1. Introduction

Most studies on capital structure in Nigeria have not been able to discriminate between spontaneous financing and contractual financing choices of Nigerian firms. We are of the view that this approach may distort the actual behaviour of firms in relation to debt financing or corporate debt policy in Nigeria. For instance, Brockington (1993) argues that cost of trade creditors is generally nil, it also constitutes a reduction in working capital requirement rather than a source of finance in itself. Other creditors like unpaid taxes may ordinarily be regarded "free" source of finance. The amount of these sources of funds depends on other factors that are obviously different from the level of finance required for long term financing of a business while they cannot normally be called on at will, as postulated in the capital structure theories.

Our position in the foregoing is anchored on the early stage of development of capital structure theory. Modigliani and Miller (1963) based their argument on role of capital structure with emphasis debt-equity mix . The account of Myers (1977, p.147) on the MM proposition states that "Modigliani and Miller (MM) have suggested (1963, p. 111) that firms maintain 'reserve borrowing capacity' - although the need for such flexibility is not clear in the frictionless capital markets MM rely on- and that the incremental tax advantage of borrowing declines as more debt is issued and interest tax shields become less certain".

The submissions of previous authors are indicative of significant of contractual debt in capital structure analysis. Durand (1959) submitted that debt policy of firms may reflect imperfect or incomplete capital markets. Jaffe (1971) and Jaffee and Russell (1976) used the credit rationing by banks and other lenders in explaining corporate borrowing. Donaldson (1963) also argued that managers avoid high debt ratios in order to protect their jobs and stabilize their personal wealth while Robichek and Myers (1966) further argued that costs of financial distress are incurred when the firm comes under the threat of bankruptcy, even if bankruptcy is ultimately avoided. Since each of these positions all point at contractual debt rather than spontaneous financing associated with trade credit, accruals and similar liabilities we argue that it is more appropriate to evaluate capital structure strictly from the long term contractual debt and equity rather than lumping it with operational debt. More recently Tripathy and Singh(2018) adopted this approach by measuring capital structure

as long-term debt to equity and argued that such Debt- Equity ratio indicates how much a company is using to finance its assets relative to the amount of value represented in shareholders' equity. They reported that quoted Indian firms have debt-equity ratio of 39:61 with a high level of dispersion.

Our approach differs from Isola and Akanni (2015) who following Welch(2011) measured leverage as total debt to total asset ratio, instead we argue that leverage is about firm capitalization or long term financing, hence measured as ratio of long term debt to equity(debt-equity mix). Firms may require additional external capital (debt and equity) to finance expansion and growth taking advantage of emerging business opportunities where internal financing is inadequate in line with the pecking order theory and asymmetry information theory of capital structure. Thus, in order that firms limit their external financial exposure management prefers internal financing through retained earnings hence would rather adopt a lower dividend pay out. This strand of argument has been sparsely examined in the Nigerian context. Owolabi and Nyang (2012) stressed that instead of distributing the high dividend and meeting the financial needs from debt capital, management retains the earnings. Hence, the lower dividend payout ratio means the lower level of debt in capital structure. High dividend paying firms would have lower retention ratio and greater tendency to resort to external debt financing and consequently higher leverage and vice versa. Hence this study examines how firm size, growth and dividend policy affect capital structure of Nigerian non-financial firms with special emphasis on long term finance rather than total funds that fail to discriminate between contractual debt and spontaneous debt as common in most studies on capital structure in Nigeria. This study is divided into five sections. Section 2 contains the literature review and the methodology is presented in section 3. The discussion of findings is presented in the fourth section while the fifth section contains the conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review

Scholars globally have identified five key theories underpinning the determination of capital structure of a firm. They are static trade-off theory, pecking order theory, modified pecking order theory, asymmetric information theory and the market timing theory. All these theories were developed to further investigate the relevance of setting optimal capital structure for a firm and the impact such would have on the value of the firm but not necessarily about what factors determine the capital structure of a firm. However, the first three are considered most relevant and therefore discussed briefly to aid understanding of the focus of the study. In practice many factors have been found to explain the financing

policy of a firm, this paper thus attempt to further explore some of those factors in the Nigerian context within the framework of some of the notable theories of capital structure.

Static Trade-Off Theory

Modigliani and Miller, M&M(1958) in their seminal paper argued that the impact of financing decision on the value of a firm is irrelevant. They submitted that the market value of a company is correctly determined as the present value of its future earnings and its underlying assets and is independent of its capital structure. However, M&M (1963) somewhat relaxed the stringent assumptions underpinning their irrelevant proposition thus paving way for the development of optimal capital structure theories under various conditions. The relaxation of the “no tax assumptions” in MM(1958) and subsequent introduction of tax benefit of interest payment on debt gave birth to the static trade-off theory. They posit that a firm trades off the cost and benefit of debt capital and makes efforts to strike between the cost and benefit of debt . It identifies the benefit of financing with debt as the tax benefit of debt, while the cost of financing with debt emanates from possible financial distress including bankruptcy costs of debt. The static trade off theory of capital structure predicts that firms will choose their mix of debt and equity financing to balance the cost and benefits of debt, and this will be the optimal capital structure of the firm for the maximization of the firm value. What matters according to this theory are the cost and benefits in any capital structure it chooses particularly, the debt capital.

Pecking Order Theory

Contrary to the prediction of the static trade-off theory, the principal proposition of the pecking order theory propounded by Myers and Majluf (1984) is that firms will not have a target optimal capital structure, but will instead follow a pecking or hierarchical order of financing choices placing internally generated funds at the top of the order, followed by debt issues, and finally only when the firm reaches its “debt capacity” new equity financing. This theory is premised on the cost implication of raising new equity or debt when compared with retained earnings which attracts no cost. Considering the cost of new issue and retained earnings, the latter is cheaper because personal taxes have to be paid by shareholders on distributed earnings while no taxes are paid on retained earnings as also there is no floatation cost incurred when the earnings are retained. The pecking order theory therefore submits that firms consider retained earnings first and if the internal funds are not sufficient to meet the investment outlays, firms go for external finance, issuing new debt before considering new equity.

Modified Pecking Order (MPO) Theory

The traditional pecking order theory holds that firms prefer internal to external financing and debt to equity if external financing is needed. Baskin (1989) using debt ratios to justify the understanding of the reactions of firm performance to the capital structure is that firms with higher past profits typically have lower leverage. However, Myers (1984) developed a MPO theory, and observed two major factors that may not allow the order of capital structure as proposed by PO theory to work; the presence of information asymmetry and financial distress. These two financial conditions may cause a change in the order for preference of capital structure.

2.2 Empirical Review

Extant empirical studies have established the determinants of capital structure globally and they have identified several factors affecting financing decision of firms in both developed and emerging economies. The earlier argument on the determinants of capital structure was limited to the industry specifics (Rajan & Zingales, 1995; Berger, Ofek & Yermack, 1997; Bevan & Danbolt, 2001). However, recent studies of (Yinusa, Alimi & Ilo, 2016; Sofat & Singh, 2017; Vo, 2017; Khemiri & Noubbigh, 2018; Li & Islam, 2019; Moradi & Paulet, 2019; Ramli *et al*, 2019; Keoksal & Orman, 2015; Campbell & Rogers, 2018; Saif-Alyousfi *et al*, 2020) have recognized that factors driving capital structure of firms are both firm, industry and country specific. The identified factors are based on verified theories and testable hypotheses. The current study is however focused on firm specific factors in evaluation of financing choices of Nigerian non-financial firms. Although, literature has documented a wide range of factors even at the firm level, we have discussed only those considered very fundamental to our argument and have therefore discussed company size, growth, age, dividend policy, asset tangibility, and profitability of the firm.

Company Size

The trade-off theory predicts a positive relationship between size of firm and the probability that larger firms tend to be more diversified and fail less often, so size may pave way for large firm to attract more debts or equity capital to finance their operations as they are also expected to incur lower costs in issuing debt or equity (Rajan & Zingales, 1995; Berger, Ofek & Yermack, 1997). Large firms have easy access to the capital market, and they can raise more debts. They can use their size to influence the structure of capital (Saif-Alyousfi *et al*, 2020; Campbell & Rogers, 2018; Li & Islam, 2019).

Asset tangibility

The relevance of tangible assets in the determination of capital structure has been established by various studies (Khemiri & Noubbigh, 2018; Li & Islam, 2019; Drobetz and

Fix, 2003; Salawu & Agboola, 2008). Jensen and Mackling (1976) explain why conflicts of interest occur between the debt providers and shareholders. The providers of debts will always demand for security on their money and the availability or policy to increase investment in tangible assets will always favour the debt providers. Rajan and Zingales (1995) opine that if a firm has a large fraction of its assets as tangible, then assets should serve as collateral, diminishing the risk of the lender suffering the agency costs of debt and retain value of liquidation. Tangible assets, such as property, plant, and equipment, are easier for outsiders to value than intangibles, such as the value of goodwill or patent right (Frank and Goyal, 2009). Firms with few tangible assets are more sensitive to informational asymmetries (Salawu & Agboola, 2008).

Dividend Policy

Investment and financing decisions are the two main decisions in corporate finance. The payout decision is related to the financing decision. The interaction of dividend policy and firm leverage can be explained using signaling effect and contracting cost theory (Sibindi, 2016). Antoniou *et al* (2008) reports an inverse relationship between leverage and dividends in the U.S. They assert that their finding supports the view that dividend payments signal a firm's future performance and thus, high dividend-paying firms benefit from a lower equity cost of capital. Lemma and Negash (2014) also documented negative relationship using nine countries in Africa.

However, pecking order theory posits that a positive relationship exists between dividend payout and debt level. According to this theory, management prefers the internal financing to external one. Instead of distributing the high dividend, and meeting the financial need from debt capital, management retains the earnings. Hence, the lower dividend payout ratio means the lower level of debt in capital structure (Owolabi & Inyang, 2012). Impliedly dividend payment may be positively or negatively related to leverage depending whether the pecking order or information asymmetry (signaling of lower cost of equity capital) prevails.

Profitability

Profitability occurs when total operating income exceeds the total non-capital expenditure. It is associated with the availability of internal funds and thus may be associated with less leverage under the pecking order theory (Baker and Wurgler, 2002). Thus, firm leverage is negatively associated with profitability. The static trade-off theory desires low level of debt capital for firms particularly the risky ones and this signifies that capital structure and profitability are positively associated. However, pecking order theory suggests that this

relation is negative, since firms prefer internal financing and follow the sticky dividend policy. If the internal funds are not enough to meet financial requirements of the firm, it prefers debt financing to equity financing (Myers 1984).

Thus, a higher profitability of the enterprise implies a higher internal financing of investment and less reliance on debt financing, Aremu, Ekpo and Mustapha (2013). Campbell and Rogers (2018) state that firms with a high volatile capital structure tend to gain less profit and lead to stricter dividend policies compared to firms with a stable capital structure. Bartoloni (2013) finds evidence to lend credence to the inverse firm leverage-profitability nexus. He finds that more profitable firms tend to use internal finance more, as implied by the negative relationship linking a firm's debt ratio and return on sales. Further he reasons that, the role of a firm's profitability in reducing the need for external finance characterises all firms, regardless of size as measured by employment, although large firms show a lower sensitivity of leverage to profit variations.

In the argument of Jensen and Meckling(1976), profitability improves the credit worthiness of firms, reduces cost of financial difficulty and lowers their cost of debt which encourages profitable firms take on more debt financing . In the view of Abor(2005) profitable firms prefer using debt as primary source of financing. However, the position conversed by Titman and Wessels(1988) is that a firm's debt and its profitability are inversely related. Sheikh and Wang (2011) found that debt ratio and profitability had a negative relationship. It is thus obvious that the relationship between debt and capital structure can be either positive or negative.

Growth

Lang, Ofek and Stulz (1996) found a negative relation between leverage and firm future growth. This relation was found to hold for firms with low Tobin's q ratio but not for high q ratio firms in high-q industries. They concluded that these findings suggest that leverage does not reduce growth for firms having good investment good investment opportunities, but it is negatively related to firms whose growth opportunities are either not recognized by the capital markets or are not sufficiently valuable to overcome the effects of their debt overhang.

Frank and Goyal (2009) contend that, growth increases costs of financial distress, reduces free cash flow problems, and exacerbates debt-related agency problems. Growing firms place a greater value on stakeholder investment. Thus, the tradeoff theory predicts that growth reduces leverage. Antoniou *et al* (2008) posits that a negative relation is expected

between growth opportunities and leverage for two main reasons. First, according to the trade-off theory, the cost of financial distress increases with expected growth forcing managers to reduce the debt in their capital structure. Second, in the presence of information asymmetries, firms issue equity instead of debt when overvaluation leads to higher expected growth.

Contradictory arguments are available between the agency cost theory and pecking order theory in respect of the relation between the growth rate and capital structure. Growth rate is negatively related with long-term debt level (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Kim & Sorensen, 1986; Saif-Alyousfi *et al*, 2020). However, pecking order theory states that internal financing is preferred to external and thus suggests a positive relationship (Myers, 1984).

Debt-tax-shield

Debt is advantageous for tax reasons. The net tax advantage of debt is the difference between the corporate tax advantage of debt (interest is corporate tax deductible) and the personal tax disadvantage of debt (Dangl & Zechner, 2004). The trade-off theory predicts a positive relationship between firm leverage and effective tax rate. As such, high tax rates increase the interest tax benefits of debt. The trade-off theory predicts that to take advantage of higher interest tax shields, firms will issue more debt when tax rates are higher (Frank & Goyal, 2009; Kahya, Ersen, Ekinici, Tas & Simsek, 2020).

Age

Age is one of the most important factors that determine the capital structure of firms (Kahya *et al*, 2020; Frank & Goyal, 2009; Aremu *et al*, 2013). The age of a firm is intricately linked to other determinants of capital structure as well. Older firms are expected to have acquired both tangible and intangible assets such to attract more debts with their good reputations. They are expected to have strong internal financial resources at their disposal.

Hyytinen and Pajarinen (2008) support that older firms' capital structure is in line with the pecking order theory. Notwithstanding the abundance of free cash flow, conventional wisdom dictates that older firms seek financing from the debt markets first. Thus the prediction is that firm leverage is positively related to age (Yildirim *et al*, 2018).

Risk

In finance parlance, risk is the probability of a loss occurring resulting in the impairment of earnings Bartoloni (2013). In the context of firm financing, risk measures the volatility of cash flows or earning prospects of a firm. The trade-off theory predicts a negative relationship between firm-leverage and risk. In other words a firm that has highly volatile

cash flows must avoid debt financing. The intuition behind is that, highly volatile cash-flows could result in financial distress. According to Antoniou *et al* (2008), firms with high earnings volatility carry a risk of the earnings level dropping below their debt servicing commitments. Ishola and Akanni(2015) notes that volatility represents a firm's probability of financial distress, and it is generally expected to have an inverse relationship with leverage. In their study of a sample of a balanced panel data of 63 non-financial firms in Nigeria measured volatility of as standard deviation of earnings before interest and tax and positively correlated with leverage. Volatility was found to have negative effect on leverage in the pooled OLS but contrarily was positive for both fixed and random effects models although not significant in any of the cases.

Agency cost theory suggests negative relation between the capital structure and business risk. The studies carried out in India and Nepal also show the contradictory evidence on the relation between the risk and debt level(Sharma, 1983, Chamoli 1985 and Garg, 1988)

Ownership Structure

The ownership structure of a firm has been recently identified as one of the factors that can influence the financing decision. Agency theory has suggested managerial ownership as one of the convincing ways to reduce to conflicts of interest between the principal and the agents (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Ownership of a firm can therefore be private but indigenous, or state or foreign ownership or mixture. Dewenter and Malatesta (2001) submit that state owned enterprises tend to rely on debt rather than equity while the study of Li, Yue and Zhao (2009) showed that foreign owned entities prefer equity to debt capital.

Methodology

The Data and Model Specification

The study employed a panel data set obtained the annual reports and accounts of a sample of 20 non-financial firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange from 2016 to 2021. This gives a total of 120 observations or data points over the 6-year period and 20 cross sectional units or firms used for the study.

The multiple linear regression model following the panel data format with capital structure as dependent variable is as specified in equation 1.

$$CS_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ZS_{it} + \beta_2 ZA_{it} + \beta_3 SG_{it} + \beta_4 AG_{it} + \beta_5 DP_{it} + \beta_6 Tang_{it} + \beta_7 Age_{it} + \beta_8 ROA_{it} + ROE_{it} + e_{it}$$

..1

The central objective is to examine how the size, growth and dividend policy of non-financial firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange affect their financing choices. The study investigated whether the firms adopt the use of more long term debt relative to equity financing as they get bigger in size, growth and increase their dividend pay out or otherwise. The details of the variables in terms of descriptions, measurements and *a priori* expectations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Variables Measurement and Description

Dependent		Description	measurement	A priori expectation
Capital Structure	CS	Debt to Equity Ratio	Long term Debt/Equity A	
Independent				
Size- Assets	ZA	Total value of assets in use by the firm its operations.	Natural logarithm of assets	Positive
Size- Sales	ZS	The total amount of income generated through the operating activities of the business	Natural logarithm of sales	Positive/Negative
Growth- Assets	ASGR	Asset growth rate (%)	Annual percentage change in value of total asset	Positive
Growth - Sales	SLGR	Sales growth rate (%)	Annual percentage change in sales value	Positive
Dividend Policy	DP	The proportion of earnings paid out to shareholders affects the amount retained	Measured indirectly using the retention ratio. Retention ratio (1 - DPS/EPS)	Positive/Negative

In order to derive a parsimonious model, we tested suitability of various proxies of the variables. The firm size was measured with total asset and sales value, however inclusion of both variables in the model produced a poor outcome. This is further evidenced by the strong correlation between total asset and sales ($r = 0.8940$). A similar strong correlation ($r = 0.9515$) was also obtained between sales growth and asset growth. These outcomes suggest possible existence of multicollinearity between total asset and sales on one hand and asset growth and sales growth on the other hand hence we dropped one of each pair of the strongly collinear variables. In the final model, we therefore proxied firm size by sales value and firm growth by asset growth. Thus, the final parsimonious model adopted for the study is presented in equation 2 as follows :

$$CS_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ZS_{it} + \beta_4 AG_{it} + \beta_5 DP_{it} + \beta_6 Tang_{it} + \beta_7 Age_{it} + \beta_8 ROA_{it} + ROE_{it} + e_{it}$$

...2

In establishing the *a priori* expectations, based on relevant theories and empirical evidence we hypothesize a positive relationship between firm age, tangibility, growth, and size and gearing. Older and matured firms with enough tangible assets as collateral for debt with stable growth and large firms are more attractive to the capital market for debt financing. Such firms have the tendency to have a larger proportion of debt in their financing options. On the other hand, the dividend policy and capital structure may be positive or negatively related. A firm with a high dividend pay out ratio will retain a lower amount of its earning for reinvestment and may need more external debt financing when additional funds are required. This raises its gearing ratio. On the other hand, a firm with low dividend policy retains more funds for internal financing and uses less of debt. Thus, the relationship between gearing and dividend policy will be positive for firms with high dividend payout but negative for firms with low dividend payout ratio. Profitability can be possibly positively or negatively related to gearing or capital structure.

Estimation technique

The pooled OLS model assumes that all intercepts and coefficients are the same for each cross section. The fixed effect (FE) model on the other hand assumes all intercept and coefficient are different for each cross section or firm due to their characteristics as proxied by the regressors, size, age, growth rate and profitability. Although the methods used in the FE model for considering differences in intercept include – the within the group FE, first difference FE and Least Square Dummy Variable (LSDV), we adopted the latter which has been found to be the most popular. The LSDV assigns a dummy variable to each firm to identify the intercept of each firm. The random effect (RE) model on the other hand assumes that intercepts of all firms are different due the randomness of the sample unlike

the FE which assumes that the difference in intercept is due to some factors related to the firm. The RE model uses the Generalised Least Squares (GLS) technique for its estimation to satisfy the OLS assumption of non-randomness and correct for heteroscedasticity.

In carrying out the data analysis we conducted the Breusch-Pagan and Hausman's test to determine the most appropriate choice model for our discussion. The Breusch-Pagan test conducted confirmed that there is evidence of systematic difference between the cross-section effect thus ruling out the use of pooled OLS (common intercept and coefficient) against the FE(different intercept and coefficient for each cross section). The Hausman test was conducted to make a choice between the fixed and random effect models. The null hypothesis is that the preferred model is REM against the alternative that it is the FEM. The null hypothesis is that there is no correlation between the unique errors(u_i) and the regressors in the model. The Hausman's test results gives a Chi-square statistic of 9.0375 and p-value of 0.495 ($p > 0.05$), we therefore fail to reject the null (since it is not significant) that the Random Effect model is preferred against the alternative that the Fixed Effect model is preferred. Therefore, the RE model is considered the most appropriate for discussion of result of this study.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation	Observations
Capital Structure	0.5055	0.1843	0.3647	120
Asset Growth	-3.7281	26.618	-7.1308	120
Sales growth	-4.7746	41.069	-8.6016	120

Tangibility	0.6277	0.6608	0.9499	120
Size- Ln(Asset)	23.4411	0.7913	9.8745	120
Size- Ln(Sales)	22.6746	0.8838	0.1169	120
Retention Ratio	0.7881	0.5572	0.7070	120
Age	53.8583	20.686	0.3861	120
ROA	0.0477	0.0746	0.6304	120
ROE	0.0895	0.4363	4.8749	120

Source: Authors' computation 2022

Table 2 shows the result of the descriptive statistics of the firms. It reveals that average debt-equity ratio of the firms was 50.55% of long term debt and 49.45 % equity with a coefficient of variation of 0.3647 indicating a low level of variability among the firms financing choices.

This implies that the share of capitalization of Nigerian non-financial firms is roughly equal proportion of long term debt and equity. Meanwhile Isola and Akanni(2019) found a total debt to asset ratio of 45% and a coefficient of variability of 1.16 for a sample of some non-financing firms in Nigeria from 2001-2010. Meanwhile Tripathy and Singh (2018) reported long-term debt equity ratio of 39: 61 for quoted Indian firms but with a high level of dispersion.

The firms experienced declines in their asset and sales growth rates at an average of -3.73% and 4.77% per annum from 2016 to 2021. The non-current asset (tangibility or collateral) component of the firms represented an average of 62.77% of their total asset but with a high level of disparity in their distribution as indicated by a high coefficient of variation of 0.9499. The average total assets of the firms was N15.147billion with an annual average

annual sales value of N7.038billion. The firms varied widely in their sizes both in terms of asset and sales. The firms on the average retained about 78.81% of their earnings suggesting that the firms paid out 21.19% of their earnings as dividends to their shareholders. The firms have been in operation for an average of 54 years. They are also relatively profitable generating about 4.77% and 8.95% return on assets and return on equity respectively.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix

	GEARING	SIZEA	SIZESL	ASGR	SGR	DP	Tang	AGE	ROA	ROE
GEARING	1.0000									
SIZEA	0.1416	1.0000								
SIZESL	0.3340	0.8940	1.0000							
ASGR	-0.0055	-0.1642	-0.1627	1.0000						
SGR	-0.0322	-0.1160	-0.1288	0.9515	1.0000					
DP	-0.0828	-0.1541	-0.1506	-0.0087	-0.0340	1.0000				
Tang	-0.0536	0.0732	0.0513	-0.0221	-0.0110	0.0277	1.0000			
AGE	-0.1012	-0.1129	-0.1932	-0.0436	-0.0949	-0.0187	-0.1263	1.0000		

Table 3 showed the correlation matrix for the specified model, and it revealed that variables such as asset growth rate, sales growth rate, dividend policy, collateral/tangibility, age and profitability (return on asset and return on equity) have weak and negative relationship with gearing. While firm size (measured as total assets and sales value) are moderately and positively correlated with gearing.

Table 4. Regression Results Dependent variable: Gearing

	<i>Pooled OLS</i>	<i>Fixed Effects</i>	<i>Random Effect</i>
Constant	-1.3841(1.2393)	-7.3941(4.5590)	-2.2058(1.8098)
Age	0.0018(0.0062)	0.0601(0.0759)	0.0046(0095)
SizeSL	0.2941 ^b (0.1477)	0.6187(0.6814)	0.3496(0.2170)
ASGR	0.0028(0.0046)	0.0020(0.0044)	0.0018(0.0042)
Tang	-0.0809(0.1841)	0.1311(0.1896)	0.0244(0.1768)
DP	-0.4180^c (0.2286)	-0.1151(0.2259)	-0.2330(0.2164)
ROA	6.7899^a (2.0964)	8.2542^a (2.2586)	7.8890^a (2.0612)
ROE	-3.8532^a (0.3330)	-4.1428^a (0.3283)	-4.0384^a (0.3130)
	Adj.R ² =0.5414 F-stat.=21.0704 F(prob)=0.0000	Adj.R ² =0.6521 F-stat.=9.5799 F(prob)=0.0000	Adj.R ² =0.5886 F-stat.=25.3189 F(prob)=0.0000

Note : a: $p < 0.01$; b: $p < 0.05$; c: $p < 0.10$

Standard errors in parentheses

Source: Author's computation 2022

Discussion of Findings

The panel data result based on REM presented in Table 4 shows that the age, asset growth, collateral(tangibility), return on asset, and sales value have positive effect on the gearing of the firms. On the other hand, factors like retention ratio and return on equity have negative impact on gearing. Surprisingly, only measures of profitability have significant impact on gearing, but their effects are in opposite directions. While return on asset has positive effect, conversely return on equity has negative and significant effect on gearing. In the first instance the positive and significant influence of ROA supports the static trade off theory of capital structure. Meanwhile, improvement in returns on equity of the firms significantly leads reduction in gearing supporting the pecking order theory of Myers and Majluf (2004). Adesola (2009) found conflicting positive and or negative influence of return on asset on capital structure of Nigerian firms under various model specifications across different years. However, the mean return on asset from 1996-2006 has a negative and significant influence on capital structure while others like firm size and growth were insignificant.

While increase in returns on total funds or asset available to the firms without discrimination about the funding sources encourages firms to increase their debt financing, contrarily equity holders prefer their firms cut down on their debt financing as returns on equity improves.

Although one would have expected profitability to have similar impacts irrespective of how it is measured, surprisingly this is not so. Shareholders would want to minimize their firm's risk as such profitable firms would prefer minimizing their gearing ratio which is responsible for the inverse relationship between gearing and return on equity. Whereas the positive relationship between gearing and return on equity perhaps may be due to the fact that ROA is a broader measure of profitability where firm's profitability is measured relative to the claim of all providers of fund or all parties having a claim on all the assets of the firm without discrimination. In this instance firms would prefer to continue to increase gearing (in the more relaxed context) as long as their firms are profitable since relative to their size by relying on ROA while shareholders prefer the ROE alternative for minimizing debt. The result on ROA supports the position of Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Abor(2005) that profitability improves credit worthiness of a firm, reduces their financial difficulty, and lowers their cost of debt enabling them to take on more debt. Conversely, the negative relationship between ROE and leverage is in line with the argument of Titman and Wessels(1982) and Sheik and Wang (2018). This finding further exposes the challenge of not differentiating long term debt financing from non-contractual debt in capital structure studies.

The dividend policy of the firms is indirectly related to gearing as high dividend paying firms will have low retained earnings as expected. The payout ratio is positively related to gearing while the retention ratio is negatively related to gearing as expected but not significant.

Older and larger firms with high level of sales revenue and capacity for maintaining consistent sales growth with substantially large asset value as collateral in line with the agency theory although not very strong have the tendency to maintain a high level of gearing. Thus, age of firms, asset growth, collateral and size of Nigerian non-financial firms give management the incentive to use more of debt than equity financing.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Studies on capital structure and implications on firm value has continued to attract a great deal of attention since the seminal paper of Modigliani and Miller (1963) capital structure irrelevance proposition. Following that studies are also replete on determinants of capital structure albeit with inconsistent and conflicting conclusions. Findings have varied from the measurement of capital structure to the types of determinant variables adopted and their measurement. Variations also exists in terms of whether the determinant are measured at the firm level, industry, national macrolevel or even across markets or countries. This study thus, argued that capital structure is about firm capitalization rather sundry short-term financing as is common in most studies of this type. This study thus, measured capital structure as ratio of long-term debt to equity with a view to examining how the firm size, growth and dividend policy help shape the capital structure of Nigerian non-financial firms. The study adopted panel data obtained from annual reports and financial statements of 20 non-financial firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange from 2016-2021. We adopted both descriptive and panel data regression techniques for data analysis.

The results show that the firms on the average adopted a debt-equity ratio of 51:49 as their common financing choice. The random effect model shows that increases in firm age, asset growth, asset tangibility, sales value, or market power and profitability increase gearing of firms. However, retention ratio in line with the pecking order hypothesis and return on equity are negatively related to gearing. Surprisingly, only the proxies for profitability have significant impact of gearing of the firms but surprisingly with contradicting effect on capital structure. While high return on asset increases leverage, improvement on return on equity compels firms to cut down on debt. By implication while shareholders focus more on minimizing risk arising from high leverage by emphasizing high return on equity whereas, management not tends to shield themselves by emphasizing and relying on return on asset which generally does not discriminate between debt and equity financing.

The study therefore, recommend that firms can mitigate against the risk of high leverage by adopting a balanced dividend policy through the right earnings retention and dividend payout ratio and ensuring adequate return on their shareholders investment.

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